

DYNAMIC MECHANICAL IN-SITU ANALYSIS OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES AT 1300°C IN OXIDIZING ATMOSPHEREChristian. Kudisonga¹, Herbert. Mucha², Horst Deckmann³, Luigi Vandi-Jules⁴, Michael. Heitzmann⁵¹ The University of Queensland, School of Mechanical and Mining Engineering, Brisbane, Australia² NETZSCH GABO Instruments, GmbH, Ahlden, Germany³ NETZSCH GABO Instruments, GmbH, Ahlden, Germany⁴ The University of Queensland, School of Chemical Engineering, Brisbane, Australia⁵ The University of Queensland, Centre for Advanced Materials Processing and Manufacturing (AMPAM), Brisbane, Australia,**Keywords:** Ceramic Matrix Composite, Dynamic Mechanical analysis, PIP process, Oxidation of C/SiC**ABSTRACT**

Modern industry demands high temperature materials for future applications. Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) are good candidates to fulfil these purposes. However, when using carbon fibers a limitation is their behavior in oxidative atmosphere. This paper investigates the mechanical properties of a carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide composites (C/SiC), in an oxidative atmosphere, up to 1300°C. Very few studies have been performed on the dynamic behavior of CMCs at high temperatures. Unlike others investigations in which the strength retention is measured at room temperature (RT), here the mechanical features of a C/SiC are monitored under dynamic loads over an extended temperature range under dynamic loads. This present paper investigates the complex modulus ($|E^*|$) and the damping factor ($\tan \delta$), up to 1300°C using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (NETZSCH GABO DMA, mod. HT-EPLEXOR) and point-bending test geometry. To avoid chemical interaction between the support and the tested sample, compatible holder material were chosen. Subsequently, two C/SiC samples were tested: a silicon-coated and an uncoated C/SiC. Sapphire material – a single crystal - proved to be the most suited as sample holder material for high temperature dynamic tests and as a reference sample material. In addition, it was found that the mechanical properties of C/SiC samples were not only maintained but increased up to 108% at high temperatures. The oxidation of carbon fibers is monitored by plummeting mechanical properties between 500°C and 800°C. Applying a simple protective coating such as a silicon layer, not only improved the stiffness in that temperature range but also at higher temperature. It is the method of high temperature dynamic mechanical analysis which is able to determine such material behavior up to 1500°C, a new nondestructive testing method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Technological challenges, such as space travel or sustainable energy storage require high temperature materials that withstand temperatures exceeding 2000°C [1]. The challenge for these materials is not only to withstand the temperature but also to withstand oxidising or reducing atmospheres over many and carrying structural loads at the same time. With their high melting/decomposition temperatures, Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) are part of the materials able to withstand such conditions for a long period of time. Among CMCs, carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide composites (C/SiC) are widely investigated as structural material for this pinnacle of material performance [1-3].

When exposed to high temperatures, in the presence of O₂, several physical reactions take place within C/SiC; both the matrix and fibers react with the atmosphere while the matrix expands. Those phenomena make the understanding of the oxidation processes more challenging. Many researchers, who investigated the oxidation resistance of C/SiC, often evaluated the thermal-mechanical performance by measuring the strength retention after high temperature oxidation [4-6]. However, these experiments cannot study the evolution of mechanical performance in-situ throughout the oxidation process. Very

Christian Kудisonga
Herbert Mucha
Horst Deckmann
Luigi Vandi-Jules
Michael Heitzmann

limited information is available in the open literature referring to changes of the stiffness of a C/SiC laminates as it is being oxidized at high temperatures.

This paper addresses this issue by determining the dynamic mechanical properties of a C/SiC materials from room temperature to 1300°C, in an oxidizing atmosphere. To do so, Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was used to measure the “hot” modulus and evaluate at the same time the damping factor of the CMCs.

The results show that the high temperature Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (EPLEXOR 500 N HT) as offered by Netzsch Gerätebau GmbH, Germany provides interesting new insights to the performance of this material class as they undergo oxidation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Validation of the Eplexor

The HT EPLEXOR, the High Temperature Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer manufactured by the NETZSCH Group, serves as a tool to perform dynamic mechanical investigations within the temperature range from RT to 1500°C. The HT EPLEXOR (Fig. 1) comes with both, a furnace operating up to 1500°C, and a standard thermal chamber for the temperature range from -160°C up to 500°C. The furnaces are designated for alternative use. In this paper, focus was put on the HT-use and on special HT sample holders. The modularity of the HT-EPLEXOR allows a quick change of sample holders and force sensors.

Fig 1: High Temperature EPLEXOR system

The calibration of force sensors can be performed at any external institute of testing having a license to issue the corresponding certificates. The independence of the static and dynamic load generation is a unique EPLEXOR feature that makes large static deformations (<60 mm) possible. A servo drive generates the static load up to +/- 1500N and an electrodynamic shaker the dynamic load (max. +/-150 N). The working principle of the apparatus is illustrated Fig 2 left.

To perform a measurement (Fig 2 right) e.g. within a temperature sweep, a small static contact load is firstly applied to simply touch the sample and maintained through the experiment to ensure that the sample remains in contact with the holder. During the second step the static target load selected for this test is applied, followed by the dynamic load. During the temperature sweep, the sample temperature increases at a constant pre-defined heating rate from 3 to 10°C/min.

Fig 2: Sketch of the modular, unique EPLEXOR design (left) and a progress of a temperature sweep in time (right)

The stiffness and the mechanical damping of materials can be expressed as one entity, the complex modulus E^* . It depends on parameters as e.g. the temperature, load conditions and frequency. Chemical reactions inside the test sample or within the contact areas between sample and holder complicate the interpretation of the results and artefacts based on such effects must be excluded.

To avoid such sample/holder interactions, a proper material selection is indispensable in mechanical testing at high temperatures. The sample holder must be chemically inert both with respect to the furnace atmosphere and with respect to the sample itself. The same applies for the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), both the sample and holder should have similar CTE. Materials in a single crystal structure like sapphire are advantageous for HT-DMA. They can be used, both as holders and as reference samples with well-defined mechanical and thermal properties.

The sapphire bar and rolls proved to be suited for high temperature bending tests. A prototype of a sapphire 3-point flexure holder is shown Fig 3. The rolls are placed at the desired span, the sample is carefully laid on the rolls and a small contact force is applied.

Fig 3: Sapphire 3-Point Bending set up

A sapphire/roll holder set up is used to characterize a sapphire sample (50 mm x 7 mm x 1 mm). The arrangement is depicted in Fig 3 and the result are shown Fig 4. As expected for single crystal samples, the result does not give any indications of sliding or phase change effects. Approximately 3% of

hysteresis is observed. This is likely a consequence of the heat capacity of the sample and a resulting lag in the heating and cooling curve. We can conclude that sapphire/roll holders are suitable and do not affect the mechanical properties of the glass sample.

Fig 4: Dynamic Mechanical test of a sapphire sample

As another real life proof of the holder concept and system calibration, two glass samples are tested up to 700°C (Fig 5). The elastic modulus $|E^*|$ demonstrates to be independent of the temperature before approaching the glass transition area. The very low mechanical damping ($\tan \delta$) is a characteristic of glasses and reflects the fact that the dissipation of mechanically introduced energy is almost negligible until softening starts.

Fig 5: Dynamic mechanical test a glass sample

(3Hz, heating rate 3°C/min)

2.2 Test and characterization

2.2.1 Specimen preparation

Flat C/SiC specimens were manufactured by Polymer Infiltration Pyrolysis (PIP) at the University of Queensland. Twenty layers of unidirectional pitch fibers were laid down in a 0/90° pattern and hot pressed with a preceramic resin to reach a fiber volume fraction of 50%. Following that, twelve pyrolysis cycles were conducted to reduce the porosity. The pyrolysis were performed up to temperatures of 1600°C in an argon atmosphere. The obtained composites were cut to the final size of 50 x 12 x 4.5 mm using a water jet. To prevent the oxidation during the test, silicon powder (American Element) was sprayed onto all outer composite surfaces and fired in an argon atmosphere at 1500°C to obtain a continuous silicon layer.

2.2.2 Microstructure analysis

The microstructure was assessed by Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (JEOL 7100). The open porosity and bulk density of the composites were measured by Archimedes method according to the standard ASTM C8302.2.

2.2.3 Dynamic mechanical analysis

The dynamic mechanical analysis of the C/SiC materials was performed using the HT-EPLEXOR in a 3-points bending configuration. The span to thickness ratio was 10, with a heating and cooling rate of 10°C/min, from room temperature to 1300°C. A static load of 45 N was firstly applied on the composite surface, before superimposing a dynamic load of 55 N at 3 Hz.

Figure 6:3-point bend set up on the HT Eplexor

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Evolution of microstructure

The porosity and the bulk porosity are gathered Table 1. As expected, the porosity increased after oxidation as oxidized fibers leave pores. The density also decreases by 20% after the high temperature oxidation, which accounts for the high porosity and the phase change of the matrix. Comparable results are obtained in literature [7].

Before oxidation		After oxidation	
Porosity (%)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Porosity (%)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)
18	1.94	42	1.54

Table 1: Porosity and bulk density of a C/SiC before and after testing

The micrographs of a silicon-coated C/SiC after oxidation at 1300°C is shown Fig 7.

Fig 7: Morphology of the silicon-coated C/SiC a) at the center and b) near the surface

From these pictures, it can be seen that a high amount of fibre pull-out is observed suggesting a weak interfacial bonding between the matrix and the fibre. When the matrix endures stress, microcracks initiate from the matrix and find their way to the fibre/matrix interface. The micro crack propagates along the fibre axis until pulls out once the strain to failure of the fibre is reached. Ceramic matrices being brittle, a certain extent of debonding is needed to prevent a brittle failure. The microscopy evaluation showed that in the centre of the specimen, a majority of fibres remain intact. However, it is worth noting that even in the centre a small number of fibres is consumed by oxidation (see Fig 7A). On the other hand, close to the outer surface, all fibers are found to be severely oxidized, with only small fibre ends surviving the two temperature cycles (Fig 7B). Despite the silicon layer, the oxidation of carbon fibres penetrates all the way through the sample.

3.2 High temperature flexural loading

Both storage modulus and loss modulus are shown Fig 8. It can be seen that the storage modulus is predominant throughout the test for both cycles indicating an elastic behaviour of the composite. Therefore, only $|E^*|$ known as complex modulus ($E^* = E' + E''$) will be further displayed.

Fig 8: Storage and loss modulus of an uncoated C/SiC

The differences of the oxidation behaviour of coated and uncoated C/SiC are investigated. Results are shown in Fig 9 ($|E^*|$) & Fig 10 ($\tan \delta$).

Fig 9: Complex modulus of coated and uncoated C/SiC

Fig 10: Damping factor of a silicon-coated and uncoated C/SiC

The complex modulus of the samples is to found to be around 44 GPa for both samples, a value which is higher than previous work investigating the dynamic behavior of ceramic matrix composites reported [8, 9]. The mechanical response can be divided in 4 temperature ranges.

For $T < 500^\circ\text{C}$, in both cases, the complex modulus experienced a gradual increase, which can be related to a stiffening of the matrix (44 GPa to 58 GPa). As for the $\tan \delta$, which represents the damping losses of the material, it is found to be low, indicating a quite homogenous material with no significant damage [8].

For the $500^\circ\text{C} < T < 800^\circ\text{C}$ region, the complex modulus of the uncoated C/SiC drops from 58 GPa to 53 GPa, which indicates a beginning of fiber degradation due to oxidation. At low temperatures, carbon fibers are known to start oxidizing [10]. The oxidation of carbon fibers follows the following scheme:

Christian Kudisonga
Herbert Mucha
Horst Deckmann
Luigi Vandi-Jules
Michael Heitzmann

No similar reduction in modulus is observed for the silicon-coated sample. The silicon layer applied on the composite surface prevented the diffusion of oxygen quite efficiently. Many researchers have shown that in this temperature range, the oxidation kinetics is controlled by the carbon/oxygen reaction [10-12]. In the case of the uncoated sample, microcracks resulting from the expansion of the fibers and the matrix are open, allowing the oxygen to diffuse within the layers and react with the carbon fibres. Additionally, the fatigue loading is accompanied by the repeated opening/closing of slit pores.

For $800^{\circ}\text{C} < T < 1300^{\circ}\text{C}$, the slope of the complex modulus changed, which can be interpreted as a further stiffening of the matrix or a phase change [13]. The complex modulus of the silicon coated sample demonstrated a substantial increase, from 64 GPa (at 800°C) to 101 GPa (1214°C), which represents a 58% increase. As for the uncoated sample, the complex modulus rose to a much lower extent, i.e from 52 GPa (at 800°C) to 68 GPa (at 1144°C). $\tan \delta$ also exhibits a substantial increase at 900°C , which is closely related to microstructural variances. This is similar to published results of dynamic measurements of unidirectional Carbon/Carbon composites (C/C), where a modulus enhancement was observed at high temperatures. The authors argued that the increase of modulus was the result of the matrix crystallization into a more graphitic structure along the unidirectional fibers, which led to an higher stiffness [14]. Fitzer and al [12] came to the same insight and showed that C/C had improved mechanical properties at high temperature. This might be due to the annealing of defects, closure of (stress distributed) microcracks and the change of the fracture behaviour of the composite. A combination of these phenomena would lead to an increased strength and stiffness between 10-60% above 1000°C , which is comparable to our findings [12]. Researchers also reported defects being annealed in a C/SiC material, where carbon fibers stretched to some extent under the combined effect of high temperature and mechanical load, resulting in increased fracture strengths [15]. In our study, the silicon carbide matrix is not only reinforced with carbon fibres but it also got a protective coating that reacted with the atmosphere. The proposed reasons for the modulus increase are the following:

- Annealing of defects: The combined thermal and mechanical load straightens the fibre leading to improved properties.
- CTE changes: As the temperature increases, the CTE of fibres and matrix changes as well leading to shear forces at the fibre/matrix interface. The CTE change might favour the crack closure resulting in improved mechanical properties.
- Self-healing: When oxidized, SiC based materials produce SiO_2 that fills pores. The SiO_2 has a lower CTE compared to SiC reducing the thermal mismatch and the microcracks ($0.7 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ vs $4 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- Phase changes: In an inert atmosphere, the preceramic precursor is known to produce an amorphous SiC up to 1100°C . When heated at higher temperature, it crystallises as β -SiC. A prolonged exposure to these temperatures might increase the modulus.

The oxidation of carbon fibers is controlled by the diffusion of reactants as shown Fig 11 . Therefore, an expansion of the matrix narrows the pores and impedes the oxidation of carbon fibre [11]. Meanwhile, silicon based materials start oxidizing, protecting the fibre via the formation of a silica layer (SiO_2), which acts as an oxygen barrier.

Fig 13: Complex modulus of a silicon-coated C/SiC during the two cycles

Fig 12: Damping factor of a silicon-coated C/SiC during the two cycles

The variation of the complex modulus for the different samples are gathered Table 2:

	Silicon coated C/SiC			
	Before oxidation	During	After oxidation	Δ Before/After (%)
$ E^* $, (GPa)	43	107	22	-49

Silicon coated C/SiC (2nd run)				
	Before oxidation	During	After oxidation test	Δ before/After (%)
E^*, (GPa)	22	69	11	-50

Uncoated C/SiC				
	Before oxidation	During	After oxidation	Δ Before/After (%)
E^*, (GPa)	45	72	7	74

Table 2: Evolution of the complex modulus of a C/SiC before, during and after oxidation

As expected, the unprotected C/SiC experienced the largest decrease of stiffness, while protected C/SiC showed a less severe reduction. These results are in line with the literature where similar reductions were reported [5, 16].

4 CONCLUSION

The influence of the mechanical support and their potential chemical interaction with the sample to be tested has been investigated. The choice of sapphire materials for both sample holders and rolls has proved to be an appropriate solution for high temperature testing. The results show that high temperature dynamic analysis as realized by the NETZSCH HT-EPLEXOR can provide valuable new insights in the behaviour of high temperature materials as e.g. C/SiC composites by in-situ analyses from room temperature up to temperature as high as 1400°C. It was demonstrated that C/SiC exhibits higher mechanical stiffness at high temperature, however, the explanation of this gain remains unclear as a lot of complex phenomena are taking place simultaneously. Nevertheless a number of explanations were proposed. Their clarification needs complementary microstructure analyses such as SEM or TEM. However, macroscopic consequences of the microscopic processes manifest themselves in a significant increase of the modulus of a C/SiC sample (up to 107%) at high temperatures. The results also showed that during cooling, the sample endures additional damages, which degrade mechanical properties. These findings point the fact that the oxidisation protection of carbon fibre reinforced C/SiC is still the most crucial matter on the long term. Vice versa for short term light weight applications, C/SiC already offer benefits when suited coating are applied. The HT-DMA in all cases can provide objective material data to assess their high temperature performance and limits.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge the facilities, and the scientific and technical assistance, of the Australian Microscopy & Microanalysis Research Facility at the Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis, The University of Queensland.

1. Ortona, A., et al., *Tubular Si-infiltrated SiCf/SiC composites for solar receiver application—Part 1: Fabrication by replica and electrophoretic deposition*. Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, 2015. **132**: p. 123-130.
2. A. Paul, D.D.J., et al., *UHTC Composites for hypersonic applications*. American Ceramic Society. **91**.
3. Glass, D.E., *Ceramic Matrix Composite (CMC) Thermal Protection Systems and Hot Structures for Hypersonic Vehicles*. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 2007.
4. Yang, X., C. Zhao-hui, and C. Feng, *High-temperature protective coatings for C/SiC composites*. Journal of Asian Ceramic Societies, 2014. **2**(4): p. 305-309.
5. Xiang, Y., et al., *Oxidation behavior of oxidation protective coatings for PIP–C/SiC composites at 1500° C*. Ceramics International, 2012. **38**(1): p. 9-13.
6. Sun, Z., et al., *Verification and prediction of residual strength of C/SiC composites under non-stress oxidation*. Journal of Materials Science, 2014. **49**(23): p. 8192-8203.
7. Ma, X., et al., *Microstructure and mechanical behaviors of T700 carbon fiber reinforced C/SiC composites via precursor infiltration and pyrolysis*. Materials Science and Engineering: A, 2016. **666**: p. 238-244.
8. Odeshi, A.G., H. Mucha, and B. Wielage, *Manufacture and characterisation of a low cost carbon fibre reinforced C/SiC dual matrix composite*. Carbon, 2006. **44**(10): p. 1994-2001.
9. Li, Y., et al., *Mechanical behavior of LSI based C/C-SiC composites subjected to flexural loadings*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2017. **95**: p. 315-324.
10. G.Savage, *Carbon-Carbon Composites*. 1993.
11. Naslain, R., et al., *Oxidation mechanisms and kinetics of SiC-matrix composites and their constituents*. Journal of Materials Science, 2004. **39**(24): p. 7303-7316.
12. Fitzer, E. and L.M. Manocha, *Carbon reinforcements and carbon /carbon composites / E. Fitzer, L.M. Manocha*. 1998, Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany ; New York: Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany ; New York : Springer.
13. Crosbie, G. and R. Allor, *Dynamic mechanical properties of ceramics and ceramic composites at elevated temperatures*. Journal of engineering for gas turbines and power, 1997. **119**: p. 15.
14. Meyer, R.A. and S.R. Gyetvay, *Carbon-Carbon Composites*, in *Petroleum-Derived Carbons*. 1986, American Chemical Society. p. 380-394.
15. Wu, D., et al., *Thermo-mechanical properties of C/SiC composite structure under extremely high temperature environment up to 1500 °C*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 2016. **90**: p. 424-431.
16. Yang, X., et al., *Evolution of microstructure and mechanical properties of PIP-C/SiC composites after high-temperature oxidation*. Journal of Asian Ceramic Societies, 2017. **5**(3): p. 370-376.